

SOLENT UNIVERSITY

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MSc International Maritime Business

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SKILLED SEAFARER RETENTION, ATTRACTION AND DISCOURAGEMENT -
REASONS, CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

2021

This project is submitted towards the fulfilment of the Degree of

MSc International Maritime Business

at Solent University

September 2021

Acknowledgments

First of all, I would like to thank my supervisor for the overall help and support in conducting my dissertation. I would also like to thank all shipping executives and students that accepted to participate in my research, through which I had the opportunity to enrich my findings with authentic and up-to-date primary data with respect to my research project. Last but not least, I would like to thank my family for the overall help and support throughout the very difficult and demanding process of conducting this dissertation.

Abstract

The aim of this dissertation was to analyze the case of the existence of skilled labour in the Greek shipping industry as a function of job satisfaction. 90 senior and middle managers of Greek shipping companies participated in a quantitative survey with questionnaires (JSS scale, Spector, 1994). Research findings indicated that shipping managers working in the Greek shipping industry illustrated high levels of job satisfaction, revealing the dynamics and the potential of the domestic maritime sector. The Greek shipping industry has managed to develop a working climate that satisfies the people that are working in it. The four factors in which participants revealed the highest levels of job satisfaction were (in order of importance): communication, nature of work, fringe benefits and contingent rewards. In contrast, weaknesses in terms of job satisfaction were identified in: supervision, pay, and operating conditions. Moreover, the levels of job satisfaction were differentiated according to gender, age and position in the company. On the other hand, educational background did not influence the responses of seafarers. In particular, men, seniors and older employees illustrated significant higher levels of job satisfaction compared to women, middle level managers and younger officers respectively. However, shipping firms should apply practices for improving the levels of job satisfaction of females and middle level managers (who in most of the cases are younger) for ensuring equity and fairness inside the organization. Overall, job satisfaction is a critical issue that had been accurately addressed by Greek maritime organizations. Nevertheless, there is room for improvement in the certain field, as a means of constituting the job of seafarers as ever more attractive.

Keywords: Shipping industry, seafarers, shipping hazards, job satisfaction

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1. Introduction

1.1. Research Aims and Objectives

The aim of this dissertation is to analyze the case of the existence of skilled labour in the Greek shipping industry as a function of job satisfaction. More specifically, the dissertation has the following objectives:

- ✓ To investigate the attractiveness of maritime officer positions in Greek naval companies
- ✓ To assess the influence of job satisfaction in employee retention in the professional reality of Greek maritime officers
- ✓ To investigate the perceptions of Greek shipping students regarding their future profession
- ✓ To explore the motivation of Greek shipping students to pursue their field of study professionally in an applied fashion
- ✓ To determine the overall level of job satisfaction among Greek maritime officers
- ✓ To examine the extent to which subcomponents of job satisfaction influence overall satisfaction among Greek maritime officers
- ✓ To provide implications regarding what shipping companies and shipping authorities shall do, in order recruit and retain skilled labour, as a means of dealing with shortage of labour and further maintaining the commercial effectiveness and safety of shipping services

1.2. Background of the Study

Over the last decade, it has been proven that the fulfillment of the objectives and goals of a company is closely tied to factors that affect its employees. The employment of highly skilled personnel is an absolute necessity for an organization, in order to secure and maintain a competitive advantage in the contemporary global economy. There are several other factors that may influence the success of an organization, but the skills and talent that employees bring to the table are perhaps the most vital assets. While

policies and strategies can be replicated on paper, the quality of employee talent, commitment and passion cannot (Battacharya, 2015). Without the correct mix of human resources, no policy or strategy can be realistically expected to succeed. The attraction of skillful applicants needs to be therefore addressed by an efficient recruitment process on a basic level and their maintenance needs to be addressed secondarily by strategic HR planning (Sidorcuka & Chesnovicka, 2017).

A significant body of research supports that there is a growing necessity for talented and skilled employees in the contemporary global market (Horwitz, 2013). In the maritime industry, things are not different. From the increasing economic globalization, which has been unfolding after the second World War, to the financial crisis in 2008, the shipping industry underwent a series of transitions that led to changes in the demand for seaborne trade. Recently, this demand has been increasing to outpace the supply of skilled employees available. According to the latest manpower report by the Baltic and International Maritime Council (BIMCO), in collaboration with the International Chamber of Shipping (ICS), in 2015 there was a shortage of 16,500 maritime officers, or 2.1% of total demand. This number is projected to increase by 2025 to 147,000, or 18.3% of total demand, due to an expansion of the needs of the industry and a projected shortage of skilled labor to service global merchant fleets (BIMCO/ICS, 2015).

According to Fei (2008), the fact that seafarers belonging to the newer generations do not view seafaring as a lifetime occupation, unlike older generations, has driven the maritime industry to undergo operational changes. It is, thus, apparent that new strategies need to be devised for the attraction and retention of skilled seafarers. Such strategies need to be adapted to the specific needs of employees in relation to the job reality, as well as to the digital landscape that defines the modern job search.

1.3. Research Rationale

The study focuses on the case of Greece with regard to seafarer shortage for various reasons. Firstly, Greece is one of the most prominent maritime nations, owning and controlling one of the largest collections of ships in the world. Indeed, the total market share of maritime companies in Greece amounts to 17.3%, while 774 ships carry the Greek national flag and 3,597 Greek maritime company ships carry foreign flags (UNCTAD, 2018). What is more, Greek seafarers form a very important part of the

maritime industry. According to the estimates of the European Commission (2006), approximately 30.920 of European seafarers are Greek. Moreover, shipping has been a significant part of the Greek economy since antiquity (Harlaftis, 2015). Last but not least, as Tsamourgelis (2007) points out, there has been a steady decline of Greek seafarers and in particular officers in the past few years, which calls for an investigation of the issue; an issue that affects not only Greece, but other countries of the world.

1.4. Structure of the Dissertation

The structure of the project is as follows:

- In the second chapter, a review of the empirical evidence and existing academic literature documenting the professional difficulties that are inherent in the seafaring profession, as well as other relevant issues associated with Human Resource Management (HRM) in shipping, is conducted. Furthermore, the review shall also refer to existing literature on the issue of job satisfaction among seafarers, as well as factors that may influence it.
- In the third chapter, the methodological tools used employed to draw conclusions and contribute to existing knowledge on the issue investigated are presented and described. Moreover, the chapter provides a detailed description of the research design used and the research the approaches selected, as well as methods of data collection and sampling, followed by the justifications for their selection.
- In the fourth chapter, the findings of the primary research are presented and analyzed, while also being critically discussed with respect to the dissertation's aims and objectives, as well as the theoretical framework developed in Chapter 2.
- In the fifth and last chapter, research findings are summarized and key conclusions are drawn regarding the subject under research. Moreover, the methodological limitations of the study are presented, based on which implications for future research are provided.

2.

Literature Review

2.1. The Role of Human Resource Management In General and in the Specific Case of the Shipping Industry

Human Resource Management (HRM) is one of the most critical functions of organizations. In particular, HRM is occupied with all aspects of an organization that are related to their human resources at an operational level, namely their wages and salaries, job description, human resource allocation, recruitment and selection, compensation and benefit plans, working schedules, motivation schemes, training and development, as well as any other daily aspect that has to do with managing human resources (Armstrong, 2006). The concept of human resources has attracted serious interest, since, apart from the daily operational level, it has been transformed into a major strategic tool for organizations. Indeed, human resources are considered as the cornerstone of effectiveness and high performance of organizations. The rationale behind this statement lies in that in order for companies to perform well and be as effective and efficient as possible, they need to recruit and select employees that have the skills, knowledge and overall potential to offer their organization the abovementioned benefits (O'Sullivan, 2014). Moreover, based on the research findings of Collins & Clark (2003), in order for organizations to be effective and highly perform, employees must also be effective and highly perform on an individual basis. It is not only the skills and knowledge of employees that count, but also the extent to which potential and existing employees have the ability to keep up with the culture, philosophy, tasks and the overall workforce of the particular case of the organization that recruits and selects them. It follows from the above that organizations need to pay very high attention to recruiting and selecting the most appropriate employees for each job position, while at the same time also paying very high attention to adequately managing their workforces, in order to bring the expected results (Collings & Wood, 2009).

Just as it happens in any other industry and business sector, HRM is also important in the context of the shipping industry as well. More specifically, HR managers in shipping are also occupied with all HR aspects of HRM, as outlined before, namely recruitment, training and development, and retention of personnel and knowledge in the shipping industry, among others. As it will be analyzed in what follows in this chapter, though, there are special conditions that the profession of seafarers is subject to, which requires more special treatment from shipping companies and their HR departments. Long periods spent at sea, health and safety issues resulting from a variety of risks on board, as well as being constantly ready to deal with emergencies deriving from perils of the sea, are only some of the special conditions that the occupation of seafarers is subject to (Fei, 2018).

The importance of HRM in shipping is also reflected in the international shipping conventions developed and put into force by the International Maritime Organization (IMO). The convention that is mostly related with human resources in shipping and particularly seafarers is the International Convention on Standards of Training, Certification and Watchkeeping for Seafarers (STCW) 1979. This convention provides the basic requirements on training, certification and watchkeeping for seafarers on an international level. The STCW convention specifically provides specific requirements regarding the training and qualifications of certain positions on board, especially those that are considered as critical for the safe operation of ships, namely crew members and officers in the engine department, radiocommunication and radio personnel, special training requirements for personnel on certain types of ships, emergency, occupational safety, medical care and survival functions, as well as watchkeeping (Christodoulou-Varotsi & Pentsov, 2007). The International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) and specifically its International Safety Management (ISM) Code suggests that that every single crew member on board shall be able to perform his duties adequately and this adequacy must be constantly controlled and monitored, as a means of enhancing maximum safety at sea (IMO, 2021). Apart from IMO, the International Labour Organization (ILO) has developed the Maritime Labour Convention 2006, which provides minimum requirements regarding the working conditions that seafarers shall be offered by their employers. In brief, the convention provides issues like the maximum hours of work, the minimum hours of rest, payment arrangements, appropriate age ranges and

nationalities, issues of health and hygiene on board, recruitment and placement services, accommodation, food and catering, accident prevention and complaint procedures for seafarers (ILO, 2021).

2.2. The Profession of Seafarers and its Attractiveness

Despite the above, there are also disadvantages associated with being a seafarer, which undermines the attractiveness of the particular profession, thereby also leading to making it difficult to attract new seafarers in the shipping business, as well as retain existing ones. More specifically, the seafaring profession is characterized by high levels of stress (Oldenburg, Baur & Schlaich, 2010). It also encompasses a great deal of risk pertaining to exhaustion of both physical and mental nature (Hystad & Eid, 2016; Gander, Van der Berg & Signal, 2008). Seafarers are often required to make decisions on the spot, especially in cases of emergencies. The particular profession becomes even more challenging in the case of officers, who often have to deal with underqualified subordinates. The high leadership responsibilities of officers and particularly senior ones produce intense stress (Oldenburg, Jensen, Latza & Baur, 2009).

Furthermore, seafarers often have to be separated from their family for long periods of time, which results in some of them feeling lonelier than others (Carotenuto, Molino, Fasanaro, Angioli, Saturnino, Sibilio & Amenta, 2013). The fact that seafarers must embark on contract bound journeys for weeks or months on end means that they shall inevitably be away from their family and closer or wider social environment (Oldenburg et al., 2009). Social isolation and separation from loved ones are among the most prominent stressors, apart from the more practical and on-the-job stressors that were outlined before. In particular, separation from loved ones is particularly concerning for most, and strongly related to feelings of loneliness when aboard the ship (Carotenuto et al., 2013; Jepsen, Zhao & Van Leeuwen, 2015). Apart from the distance from family and social relations, though, the profession of seafarers is so demanding that often becomes incompatible with family demands. As this is also the case with other demanding and stressful professions, seafarers also often find themselves unable to satisfy both their job and their family. This phenomenon is conceptualized as Work-Family Conflict and has been well studied in seafarer populations, proving to be one of the major factors impacting the mental and

physiological health of seafarers (Thomas, Sampson & Zhao, 2003). Indeed, as Kim & Jang (2016) also note, crew members, irrespective of their position on board, endure high levels of stress for inordinate amounts of time as a result of their altered lifestyle of social isolation and damaged family relationships. This work-family conflict, combined with increased stress, can even cause severe negative mental health outcomes, such as the emergence of psychotic symptoms among marine officers (Kim & Jang, 2016).

At the same time, seafarers communicate with coworkers from a great variety of backgrounds, which may cause communicational difficulties and often conflicts. As it is obvious, and as also analyzed by Harwood (2018), the shipping industry is global in its nature. Indeed, although shipping companies are said to have a base where their headquarters are located, they sail with international flags and they also occupy a highly diverse workforce in terms of nationality and, thus, religious, cultural and other demographic aspects. Apart from being highly difficult for HR managers to deal with diverse workforces, as it happens with all international organizations in all sectors, employees working in international organizations and, thus, seafarers, also have to cope with different people from different nationalities, with whom they may not have the same interests. This indeed may cause communicational difficulties among seafarers, especially those that do not have many years of experience in the particular profession.

Working on a ship also entails long hours of work, leading to sleep deprivation and fatigue in the long run (Besikci, Tavacioglu & Arslan, 2015; Jepsen, Zhao & Van Leeuwen, 2015). The above refer to physical fatigue, whereby people find it difficult to perform sometimes even their simplest daily tasks, because of their physical exhaustion. As analyzed before, fatigue may also be psychological -mental, whereby people do not have the ability to keep concentrated on their task, often finding it difficult to stay awake, even while working. According to Allianz Global (2019), preventing fatigue is a critical issue in the shipping industry, if it is taken into account that about 80% of ship groundings that have taken place after midnight and before dawn shall be attributed to seafarers' fatigue. It is also noteworthy that based on the study held by the Universities of Queensland and Western Australia, 1 in 5 seafarers have reportedly experienced some levels of acute fatigue and/or chronic fatigue and

recommends that an effective fatigue management system is crucial for the maritime industry more than ever (Safety 4 Sea, 2019).

In the same context with the above, seafarers have to endure long periods without physical contact with others and with scarce opportunities for any form of entertainment (Oldenburg, Hogan & Jensen, 2013). This is related with both fatigue and the psychological problems associated with the profession of seafarers, as discussed above. Indeed, when seafarers are absent from entertainment for long, this adds to their fatigue, which, as analyzed before, may endanger safety at sea in terms of various aspects of shipping operations. At the same time, this also adds to their psychological distress and feelings of loneliness, feeling that their family members, friends and other members of their closer social environment keep on entertaining themselves, when they are not there as well.

Lastly, working on a ship means that one has to endure noise, the constant movement of the ship, vibrations caused by machinery and waves, and intense heat, particularly in internal places close to the machinery (Oldenburg & Jensen, 2012). The research findings of Oldenburg, Felten, Hedtmann & Jensen (2020) suggest that the above are indeed some of the most important stressors that seafarers have to deal with during their working life on board, which also form some of the main reasons for which they may decide to stop working as seafarers after some time. Indeed, the abovementioned researchers accompanied the seafarers of a German container shipping company in six of their voyages and discussed the physical difficulties that seafarers said that they mostly experience on board. According to their responses, the most frequent problems they face while on board are difficulties associated with noise and vibrations. In particular, the highest noise levels were found in the engine room, in the workshop and on deck, while both vibrations and heat were mostly reported by seafarers working in the engine room. The seafarers stated that although they have not used to such difficulties, which they call them routine ones, they also stress the need for shipping companies to maintain the best possible working conditions on board, if they wish to retain their seafarers.

2.3. Job Satisfaction – General Overview, Importance and Factors

Determining it

As the term implies, job satisfaction is the term referring to the extent to which employees and overall organizational members are satisfied with their job. There are various factors that determine the extent to which employees are satisfied with their job. Factors like remuneration and benefits, salaries, health and hygiene, work schedules, the effectiveness in allocating tasks across human resources, potential for personal development and promotion, the nature and quality of peers, supervisors and managers are some of the basic and somehow objective factors that determine job satisfaction. There are also factors associated with the job tasks themselves, namely their volume and level of difficulty, together with the ability of employees to successfully accomplish their daily tasks in reasonable time (Spector, 1997).

Apart from the factors that have been addressed so far, job satisfaction is also determined by recruitment and selection. As Schaufeli & Bakker (2004) point out, during recruitment and selection, organizations have the ability to choose from a big pool of candidates those that are not only the most skilled and qualified, but also those that are more likely to perform specific duties in the best way, as well as those that are mostly likely to fit with the culture of the organization. At the same time, though, recruitment and selection is an important process not only for organizations and HR managers, but also for candidates, since, during the same process, they are not only selected by an organization, but also they select the organization to work for. It follows from the above that the selecting the most appropriate and willing employees leads to their higher potential job satisfaction and, thus, retention.

Job satisfaction is highly linked with motivation in the workplace, thereby offering the concept a highly subjective substance. In specific, the various theories of motivation in the workplace differ in terms of which factors motivate employees (or demotivate them). However, what they all have in common is that they point out that different employees are motivated by different factors in their workplace, which are consistent with the different needs they wish to satisfy through their job (Thompson & Phua, 2012).

The concept of job satisfaction is important both for employees as individuals and their organizations as a whole. Indeed, the research findings of Bakotic (2013) indicate that job satisfaction is a very important determinant of individual job performance, which in turn influences the performance of an organization as a whole. The rationale behind this assumption lies in that if employees are satisfied with their workplace and their job as a whole, then it is likely that they shall perform better, which means that the performance of their organization is also higher, since employees are keen on performing their job tasks more effectively and efficiently.

Job satisfaction is also an important determinant of employee commitment and retention. Based on the research findings of Dalkrani & Dimitriadis (2018), satisfied employees are more likely to be committed to their organization. In particular, the employees that are more likely to remain committed to their organization are those that are satisfied with social aspects of job, job characteristics and work environment, while satisfaction with promotion and rewards was not found to influence employee commitment to such an extent. At the same time, the findings of the thorough review of previous research studies held by Biason (2020) indicate that there is a long-standing, steady and positive correlation between job satisfaction and employee retention.

2.4. Job Satisfaction in the Profession of Seafarers

Just as it happens with all other industries, sectors, and profession, job satisfaction is also an important aspect in the context of the shipping industry. Job satisfaction is viewed as an extremely important factor within the shipping industry, not only because of its potential to contribute to reducing employee turnover, but also because it is tied to safety in the field (McVeigh et al, 2019). More specifically, persistently high levels of job satisfaction have been found to be correlated with higher motivation to follow safety procedure protocols and enhanced performance (Yuen et al., 2018). Reduced levels of job satisfaction on the other hand have been found to be associated with a slew of negative outcomes for the organization, as employees may become dissatisfied and demonstrate an increased desire to leave, as well as exhibit absenteeism and reduced productivity and work performance (Gershon et al., 2009; Bockerman & Ilmakunnas, 2012).

It was analyzed before that the job of seafarers is subject to high levels of stress. Based on the findings of Chung, Lee & Lee (2017), increased stress has been identified as one of the most significant causes of maritime accidents and burnout among seafarers. Crucially, high levels of stress have been found to lead to reduced levels of job satisfaction, and can also inhibit productivity among seafarers (Kim, 2013; Lucero-Prisno, 2014). Based on the above, stress, as well as other hazards of the occupation of seafarers reduce their levels of job satisfaction, thereby also making it rather challenging to retain seafarers.

It therefore follows that job satisfaction is a key element that needs to be taken into consideration when designing benefit and compensation packages for overstressed and overworked seafarers, particularly to enhance job attractiveness and retention. As Nguyen, Ghaderi, Caesar and Cahoon (2014), employee retention is the most challenging function of crew management in the context of HRM. Indeed, taking into consideration the hazards and other difficulties the job of seafarers is subject to, it follows that it is important for shipping companies and particularly their line managers to give crew members the necessary incentives to feel that they wish to work as seafarers and their job satisfaction is maintained at high levels. Showing appreciation for rewarding high performance, as well as offering work flexibility job promotions, salary increases and other benefits and bonuses are all some of the types of motivation schemes that shipping companies shall offer to seafarers, in order to drive their job satisfaction and help them in taking the decision not only to enter the shipping industry as seafarers, but also remain to it (Branch, 2007).

3.

Research Methodology

3.1. Research Design

The research design occupied for the purposes of this study was descriptive. Descriptive designs are structured around answering a specific research problem but not in a way that entails discovering the cause of a phenomenon. Rather, a descriptive design is employed to gather information for the current status of a given phenomenon and describe what is with regard to its condition in a given point in time. Descriptive designs are employed to gather large amounts of data that can be used for an extensive analysis, in order to create more sophisticated quantitative designs (Cooper and Schindler, 2014). In this paper, a descriptive design was used to examine the job satisfaction levels of seafarer officers currently employed, both overall as well as factor-by factor, so as to gain insights as to which areas could be improved to benefit employee retention. Questionnaire surveys were conducted in the context of this design.

3.2. Research Approach

The appropriate description of the research paradigm applied during the course of a study is a crucial step in detailing the research methodology, as it permits the elucidation of the nature of the links between the data and their significance in the context of their interpretation (Greener, 2008). The research approach regarding this project included quantitative elements.

Quantitative research seeks to describe reality through the numerical analysis of operationally defined variables. Quantitative data are used to prove causal relationships, to prove theories and to objectively measure certain variables that can be generalized to broader populations or used for comparisons with other measurements (Greener, 2008). The generalizability of conclusions drawn on

quantitative data is dependent on the representativeness of the sample population. Quantitative studies can be conducted either in the form of experiments or in the form of questionnaire surveys, like in the present paper.

The research approach on which quantitative methodology was based is the paradigm of positivism. Positivism is defined by clarity of description and certainty of measurement. There is no subjectivity in the interpretation of positivist conclusions. Research that is based on the positivist paradigm is based on factual evidence produced by empirical observation and clearly documented experience. The conclusions that such a philosophy allows are based on information derived from sensory experience as well as deduced through rational means. The positivist approach is geared towards the proposition and testing of concrete theories that describe consistent patterns in specific variables or phenomena, in the likeness of quasi-absolute laws (Sarantakos, 2013).

3.3. Sampling and Data Collection

Due to time and mainly resource constraints, it was not possible to attract a large enough sample size, nor to select a fully randomized representative sample. As such, the sampling method was that of snowball sampling, where the researcher comes into contact with prospective participants and uses them to recruit more participants, until a satisfactory number of participants is gathered.

In the above context, the researcher contacted officials in Greek maritime companies and asked for the contact information of working seafarer officers, so that he could later come into contact with them and distribute the questionnaire online or via phone. From the 283 working seafarers that were contacted, 94 expressed their willingness to participate and eventually 90 were those that responded to all questions of the questionnaire, thereby forming the final research sample ($N=90$). The instrument used for data collection on the variable of job satisfaction was the Job Satisfaction Survey by Paul Spector (1985) (see Appendix), an internationally validated instrument, which has enjoyed widespread use and robust empirical support in previous research (Hora, Junior & de Souza, 2018). It uses a 6-point Likert scale to score participant answers on a total of 36 questions measuring job satisfaction across 9 different facets, including monetary and non-monetary rewards, relationships with coworkers and supervisors, the nature of work and communication.

3.4. Data Analysis

Data for the quantitative part of the research was analyzed using SPSS statistics and was mainly comprised of descriptive statistics for the job satisfaction measures along with some demographics. Parametric tests were used for examining if the responses of the participants were differentiated according to their demographic features. More specifically, independent T-tests were conducted for gender and position in the company and one-way ANOVA analyses were conducted for age and educational background.

4.

RESULTS

4.1. Introduction

This chapter presents the analysis of findings of the dissertation. The analysis was conducted with SPSS v.25 and included descriptive statistics and parametric tests (T-tests and one-way ANOVA analysis). The chapter includes 12 paragraphs following mainly the structure of the questionnaire.

4.2. Sample Demographics

Table 1 shows the demographic features of the sample. As shown below, 62,2 % of the participants were males and 37,8 % were females, indicating that the shipping industry in Greece is a male dominated sector. Moreover, 8,9 % of the respondents were 18-30 years old, 48,9 % were 31-40 years old, 37,8 % were 41-50 years old and 4,4 % were more than 51. In terms of education level, the vast majority of the shipping managers were university graduates, whereas 15,6 % were high school graduates and 12,2 % were holding a Master degree or/and a PhD. Lastly, almost 70 % of the sample were middle level managers and 30 % were seniors.

Table 1: Sample Demographics

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Valid Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
<i>Male</i>	56	62,2	62,2	62,2
<i>Female</i>	34	37,8	37,8	100,0
<i>Total</i>	90	100,0	100,0	
	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Valid Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
<i>18-30</i>	8	8,9	8,9	8,9
<i>31-40</i>	44	48,9	48,9	57,8
<i>41-50</i>	34	37,8	37,8	95,6
<i>51+</i>	4	4,4	4,4	100,0

Total	90	100,0	100,0	
	<i>Frequency</i>	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
<i>High school</i>	14	15,6	15,6	15,6
<i>University</i>	65	72,2	72,2	87,8
<i>Master/Phd</i>	11	12,2	12,2	100,0
Total	90	100,0	100,0	
	<i>Frequency</i>	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
<i>Middle level Manager</i>	61	67,8	67,8	67,8
<i>Senior Manager</i>	29	32,2	32,2	100,0
Total	90	100,0	100,0	

4.3. PAY

Overall, the satisfaction of shipping managers by their pay is fluctuated in moderate levels. The overall mean was 4,08. The mean was highest in the statement “Raises are too few and far between” (reversed question), namely: 4,38.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics (Pay)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
I Feel I am Being Paid A Fair Amount For The Work I Do	90	2,00	6,00	4,3556	1,44028
Raises are too few and far between. (-)	88	1,00	6,00	4,3864	1,48890
I feel unappreciated by the organization when i think about What they pay me. (-)	90	1,00	7,00	4,1556	1,61392
I feel satisfied with my chances for salary increases.	90	1,00	6,00	3,7111	1,67764
Overall mean Score				4,08	16,6

4.4. Promotion

The overall satisfaction in the construct promotion was higher: 4,38. Indicatively, the satisfaction from the chances for promotion was 4,7 and the mean in fairness in promotions was 4,4 (see Table 3).

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics (promotion)

	<i>N</i>	<i>Minimum</i>	<i>Maximum</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
<i>There is really too little chance for promotion on my job. (-)</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,3333	1,52875
<i>Those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,4000	1,31371
<i>People get ahead as fast here as they do in other places.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	3,7556	1,69806
<i>I am satisfied with my chances for promotion.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,7111	1,69098
Overall Mean				4,34	
Score				17,2	

4.5. Supervision

The overall satisfaction in the factor supervision was 4,07 (overall score 16,2). In general terms, most of the participants did not express positive views towards their supervisors (mean: 3,4). In contrast, fairness of the supervisor was significantly higher (mean: 4,6).

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics (supervision)

	<i>N</i>	<i>Minimum</i>	<i>Maximum</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
<i>My supervisor is quite competent in doing his/her job.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	3,8444	1,69541
<i>My supervisor is unfair to me.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,6222	1,47319
<i>My supervisor shows too little interest in the feelings of subordinates.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,4000	1,34749
<i>I like my supervisor.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	3,4222	1,59337
Overall mean				4,07	
Score				16,2	

4.6. Fringe Benefits

The satisfaction of shipping managers from fringe benefits was higher (mean: 4,62, overall score 18,5). Benefits are considered as good (mean: 5,1), whereas benefits package seems that is equitable (mean: 4,51) (see table 5).

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics (fringe benefits)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>I am not satisfied with the benefits I receive.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,2667	1,71445
<i>The benefits we receive are as good as most other organizations offer.</i>	90	2,00	6,00	5,1556	,84682
<i>The benefit package we have is equitable.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,5111	1,52319
<i>There are benefits we do not have which we should have.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,5778	1,44547
Overall mean				4,62	
Score				18,5	

4.7. Contingent Rewards

The satisfaction from contingent rewards was also is relatively higher levels. In particular, the overall mean was 4,62 (overall score 18,4). Participants denoted that their work is generally appreciated (mean: 5,06), as well as that their efforts are rewarded (mean: 4,8). In contrast, the mean in the statement “There are few rewards for those who work here” was lower (see table 6).

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics (contingent rewards)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>When I do a good job, I receive the recognition for it that I should receive.</i>	90	1,00	7,00	4,4444	1,78074
<i>I do not feel that the work I do is appreciated.</i>	90	2,00	6,00	5,0667	1,10971
<i>There are few rewards for those who work here.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,1333	1,69069
<i>I don't feel my efforts are rewarded the way they should be.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,8444	1,66869
Overall mean				4,62	
Score				18,4	

4.8. Operating Conditions

The overall mean in operating conditions was 4,15 (total score: 16,6). The most negative component in this section was paperwork, a fact that reflects the complexity of the Greek business environment (see table 7).

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics (operating conditions)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>Many of our rules and procedures make doing a good job difficult.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,1778	1,69982
<i>My efforts to do a good job are seldom blocked by red tape.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,6000	1,33071
<i>I have too much to do at work.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,1556	1,72171
<i>I have too much paperwork.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	3,6667	1,77372
Overall mean				4,15	
Score				16,6	

4.9. Coworkers

What is more, satisfaction from the relationships with coworkers was good since the overall mean was 4,46 (total score: 17,8). The competence of coworkers was considered as high (mean:4,8) and for that reason participants generally like they people they are working with (mean: 4,6) (see table 8):

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics (Coworkers)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>I like the people I work with.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,6667	1,39017
<i>I find I have to work harder at my job because of the incompetence of people I work with.</i>	90	2,00	6,00	4,8000	1,29996
<i>I enjoy my coworkers.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,4222	1,47624
<i>There is too much bickering and fighting at work.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	3,9778	1,82970
Overall mean				4,46	
Score				17,8	

4.10. Nature of Work

Overall, participants exhibited high levels of satisfaction from the nature of their work. As shown in Table 9, the overall mean was 4,71 and the total score was 18,6. Shipping executives find a meaning in their work (mean: 5,22) and considered it as enjoyable (mean: 4,6)

Table 9: Descriptive Statistics (nature of work)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>I sometimes feel my job is meaningless.</i>	90	2,00	6,00	5,2222	1,15902
<i>I like doing the things I do at work.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,4000	1,50505
<i>I feel a sense of pride in doing my job.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,5556	1,41510
<i>My job is enjoyable.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,6889	1,49640
Overall mean				4,71	
Score				18,6	

4.11. communication

Finally, the highest level of satisfaction was identified in the construct “Communication”. The mean was 4,74 and the overall score 18,9 (see Table 10). Communication within the shipping organizations is considered as good (mean: 5,24), whereas top management succeeds in communicating effectively organizational goals (mean: 4,71).

Table 10: Descriptive Statistics (Communication)

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
<i>Communications seem good within this organization.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	5,2444	1,22071
<i>The goals of this organization are not clear to me.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,7111	1,50836
<i>I often feel that I do not know what is going on with the organization.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,6444	1,32657
<i>Work assignments are not fully explained.</i>	90	1,00	6,00	4,4000	1,63391
Overall mean				4,74	
Score				18,9	

Table 11 summarizes the satisfaction rates from each dimension that was involved in the questionnaire:

Table 11: Total Score - Summary of Findings

<i>Dimension</i>	Mean	Score
<i>Pay</i>	4,08	16,6
<i>Promotion</i>	4,34	17,2
<i>Supervision</i>	4,07	16,2
<i>Fringe Benefits</i>	4,62	18,5
<i>Contingent rewards</i>	4,62	18,4
<i>Operating conditions</i>	4,15	16,6
<i>Coworkers</i>	4,46	17,8
<i>Nature of work</i>	4,71	18,6
<i>Communication</i>	4,74	18,9
<i>Total score</i>	4,42	158,8

As shown above, total score was 158,8. As it is noted in the interpretation guide of the Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) developed by Spector, a total score higher than 144 signifies satisfaction from work. Therefore, Greek seafarers are satisfied from their job, revealing the dynamics of the industry for its future development.

4.12. Parametric Tests

As it was noted earlier in the methodology section, parametric tests were used for examining if the responses of the participants were differentiated according to their demographic features. Independent T-tests were employed for gender and position in the company and one-way ANOVA analysis for age and educational background.

4.12.1. Gender (T-Tests)

The results of the independent T-tests based on gender are illustrated in Table 12. As shown below, gender influenced substantially the levels of satisfaction of the

respondents. In particular, statistically significant differences were identified in the following variables: I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do ($p < 0,05$); There is really too little chance for promotion on my job ($p < 0,05$); My supervisor is quite competent in doing his/her job ($p < 0,05$); I am not satisfied with the benefits I receive ($p < 0,05$); When I do a good job, I receive the recognition for it that I should receive ($p < 0,05$); Many of our rules and procedures make doing a good job difficult ($p < 0,05$); I like the people I work with ($p < 0,05$); I sometimes feel my job is meaningless ($p < 0,05$); Communications seem good within this organization ($p < 0,05$); Raises are too few and far between ($p < 0,05$); Those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted ($p < 0,05$); My supervisor is unfair to me ($p < 0,05$); I like doing the things I do at work ($p < 0,05$); The goals of this organization are not clear to me ($p < 0,05$); My supervisor shows too little interest in the feelings of subordinates ($p < 0,05$); I feel satisfied with my chances for salary increases ($p < 0,05$); There are benefits we do not have which we should have ($p < 0,05$). In all the aforementioned statements men illustrated significant higher levels of satisfaction compared to women.

Table 12: Independent T-Tests (gender)

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Sig. (2-tailed)
<i>I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do.</i>	Male	56	4,9286	1,20389	,16088	,000
	Female	34	3,4118	1,30541	,22388	
<i>There is really too little chance for promotion on my job.</i>	Male	56	4,8929	1,35752	,18141	,000
	Female	34	3,4118	1,35104	,23170	
<i>My supervisor is quite competent in doing his/her job.</i>	Male	56	4,3571	1,38076	,18451	,000
	Female	34	3,0000	1,84226	,31595	
<i>I am not satisfied with the benefits I receive.</i>	Male	56	4,7857	1,43608	,19190	,000
	Female	34	3,4118	1,81104	,31059	
<i>When I do a good job, I receive the recognition for it that I should receive.</i>	Male	56	5,0000	1,40130	,18726	,000
	Female	34	3,5294	1,97308	,33838	
<i>Many of our rules and procedures make doing a good job difficult.</i>	Male	56	4,6429	1,50670	,20134	,000
	Female	34	3,4118	1,74282	,29889	

<i>I like the people I work with.</i>	Male	56	5,0714	1,00647	,13450	,001
	Female	34	4,0000	1,66969	,28635	
<i>I sometimes feel my job is meaningless.</i>	Male	56	5,5000	1,06173	,14188	,001
	Female	34	4,7647	1,18216	,20274	
<i>Communications seem good within this organization.</i>	Male	56	5,5714	,62834	,08396	,004
	Female	34	4,7059	1,69722	,29107	
<i>Raises are too few and far between.</i>	Male	54	4,7407	1,11905	,15228	,007
	Female	34	3,8235	1,81693	,31160	
<i>Those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted.</i>	Male	56	4,7143	1,17108	,15649	,001
	Female	34	3,8824	1,38749	,23795	
<i>My supervisor is unfair to me.</i>	Male	56	4,8214	1,37652	,18395	,005
	Female	34	4,2941	1,58648	,27208	
<i>The benefits we receive are as good as most other organizations offer.</i>	Male	56	5,1786	,81144	,10843	,113
	Female	34	5,1176	,91336	,15664	
<i>I do not feel that the work I do is appreciated.</i>	Male	56	5,2143	,98561	,13171	,750
	Female	34	4,8235	1,26660	,21722	
<i>My efforts to do a good job are seldom blocked by red tape.</i>	Male	56	4,7143	1,26080	,16848	,130
	Female	34	4,4118	1,43796	,24661	
<i>I find I have to work harder at my job because of the incompetence of people I work with.</i>	Male	56	5,1429	1,06904	,14286	,315
	Female	34	4,2353	1,45766	,24999	
<i>I like doing the things I do at work.</i>	Male	56	4,8571	1,13504	,15168	,003
	Female	34	3,6471	1,73873	,29819	
<i>The goals of this organization are not clear to me.</i>	Male	56	5,1071	1,30284	,17410	,001
	Female	34	4,0588	1,61323	,27667	
<i>I feel unappreciated by the organization when I think about what they pay me.</i>	Male	56	2,9643	1,56047	,20853	,150
	Female	34	3,4706	1,67396	,28708	
<i>People get ahead as fast here as they do in other places.</i>	Male	56	3,2143	1,73430	,23176	,158
	Female	34	4,6471	1,20309	,20633	,
<i>My supervisor shows too little</i>	Male	56	4,8571	1,16664	,15590	,000
	Female	34	3,6471	1,29994	,22294	

<i>interest in the feelings of subordinates.</i>						
<i>The benefit package we have is equitable.</i>	Male	56	4,6786	1,42838	,19087	,000
	Female	34	4,2353	1,65252	,28341	
<i>There are few rewards for those who work here.</i>	Male	56	4,4643	1,60640	,21466	,199
	Female	34	3,5882	1,70769	,29287	
<i>I have too much to do at work.</i>	Male	56	4,4286	1,64987	,22047	,119
	Female	34	3,7059	1,76720	,30307	
<i>I enjoy my coworkers.</i>	Male	56	4,7500	1,46784	,19615	,058
	Female	34	3,8824	1,34310	,23034	
<i>I often feel that I do not know what is going on with the organization.</i>	Male	56	4,5000	1,56089	,20858	,186
	Female	34	4,8824	,76929	,13193	
<i>I feel a sense of pride in doing my job.</i>	Male	56	4,8214	1,20766	,16138	,125
	Female	34	4,1176	1,62862	,27931	
<i>I feel satisfied with my chances for salary increases.</i>	Male	56	4,0000	1,74773	,23355	,033
	Female	34	3,2353	1,45766	,24999	
<i>There are benefits we do not have which we should have.</i>	Male	56	4,7857	1,35800	,18147	,028
	Female	34	4,2353	1,53857	,26386	
<i>I like my supervisor.</i>	Male	56	3,3571	1,55422	,20769	,091
	Female	34	3,5294	1,67396	,28708	
<i>I have too much paperwork.</i>	Male	56	3,0357	1,91610	,25605	,628
	Female	34	2,0588	1,32439	,22713	
<i>I don't feel my efforts are rewarded the way they should be.</i>	Male	56	4,8929	1,50971	,20174	,751
	Female	34	4,7647	1,92368	,32991	
<i>I am satisfied with my chances for promotion.</i>	Male	56	4,6071	1,58032	,21118	,742
	Female	34	4,8824	1,87107	,32089	
<i>There is too much bickering and fighting at work.</i>	Male	56	3,1071	1,73392	,23171	,476
	Female	34	2,7647	1,98569	,34054	
<i>My job is enjoyable.</i>	Male	56	4,5000	1,58401	,21167	,409
	Female	34	5,0000	1,30268	,22341	
<i>Work assignments are not fully explained.</i>	Male	56	4,0000	1,80907	,24175	,108
	Female	34	5,0588	1,01328	,17378	

4.12.2. Position in the Company

Position in the company had a slighter influence in the responses of seafarers. In more details, significant differences were identified in the four statements, namely: I am not

satisfied with the benefits I receive ($p < 0,05$); When I do a good job, I receive the recognition for it that I should receive ($p < 0,05$); Many of our rules and procedures make doing a good job difficult ($p < 0,05$); I like the people I work with ($p < 0,05$). In all these cases, senior managers exhibited higher levels of satisfaction compared to middle level managers (see Table 13).

Table 13: Independent T-Test (position in the company)

	Position in the company	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Sig. (2-tailed)
<i>I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,5082	1,36165	,17434	,146
	Senior Manager	29	4,0345	1,56941	,29143	
<i>There is really too little chance for promotion on my job.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,4918	1,54513	,19783	
	Senior Manager	29	4,0000	1,46385	,27183	,155
<i>My supervisor is quite competent in doing his/her job.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,0164	1,48876	,19062	
	Senior Manager	29	3,4828	2,04626	,37998	,164
<i>I am not satisfied with the benefits I receive.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	3,6738	1,55412	,19899	,013
	Senior Manager	29	4,5207	1,87871	,34887	
<i>When I do a good job, I receive the recognition for it that I should receive.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	3,7705	1,61651	,20697	,022
	Senior Manager	29	4,7586	1,93935	,36013	,
<i>Many of our rules and procedures make doing a good job difficult.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	3,4918	1,56656	,20058	,019
	Senior Manager	29	4,5172	1,80517	,33521	
<i>I like the people I work with.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,2541	1,42192	,18206	,016
	Senior Manager	29	4,9828	1,32613	,24626	
<i>I sometimes feel my job is meaningless.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	5,2131	1,21264	,15526	,379
	Senior Manager	29	5,2414	1,05746	,19637	
<i>Communications seem good within this organization.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	5,1967	1,33940	,17149	,910
	Senior Manager	29	5,3448	,93640	,17389	
<i>Raises are too few and far between.</i>	Middle level Manager	60	4,4333	1,49991	,19364	,546
	Senior Manager	28	4,2857	1,48716	,28105	,
<i>Those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,4754	1,27288	,16298	,667
	Senior	29	4,2414	1,40548	,26099	

<i>promoted.</i>	Manager					
<i>My supervisor is unfair to me.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,7049	1,41826	,18159	,450
	Senior Manager	29	4,4483	1,59432	,29606	
<i>The benefits we receive are as good as most other organizations offer.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	5,1803	,80640	,10325	,463
	Senior Manager	29	5,1034	,93903	,17437	,
<i>I do not feel that the work I do is appreciated.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	5,0656	1,07810	,13804	,706
	Senior Manager	29	5,0690	1,19317	,22157	
<i>My efforts to do a good job are seldom blocked by red tape.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,5574	1,31053	,16780	,990
	Senior Manager	29	4,6897	1,39139	,25837	
<i>I find I have to work harder at my job because of the incompetence of people I work with.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,8852	1,23960	,15871	,669
	Senior Manager	29	4,6207	1,42463	,26455	
<i>I like doing the things I do at work.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,5410	1,42096	,18194	,395
	Senior Manager	29	4,1034	1,65497	,30732	
<i>The goals of this organization are not clear to me.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,8361	1,46265	,18727	,226
	Senior Manager	29	4,4483	1,59432	,29606	
<i>I feel unappreciated by the organization when I think about what they pay me.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	3,1967	1,65146	,21145	,273
	Senior Manager	29	3,0690	1,55681	,28909	
<i>People get ahead as fast here as they do in other places.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	3,5574	1,65856	,21236	,723
	Senior Manager	29	4,1724	1,73347	,32190	
<i>My supervisor shows too little interest in the feelings of subordinates.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,5410	1,34875	,17269	,117
	Senior Manager	29	4,1034	1,31868	,24487	
<i>The benefit package we have is equitable.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,4918	1,51243	,19365	,150
	Senior Manager	29	4,5517	1,57176	,29187	
<i>There are few rewards for those who work here.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,2623	1,63199	,20895	,865
	Senior Manager	29	3,8621	1,80721	,33559	
<i>I have too much to do at work.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,2459	1,70934	,21886	,316
	Senior Manager	29	3,9655	1,76236	,32726	
<i>I enjoy my coworkers.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,4262	1,56481	,20035	,479
	Senior Manager	29	4,4138	1,29607	,24067	

<i>I often feel that I do not know what is going on with the organization.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,4918	1,45628	,18646	,968
	Senior Manager	29	4,9655	,94426	,17534	
<i>I feel a sense of pride in doing my job.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,5902	1,39496	,17861	,068
	Senior Manager	29	4,4828	1,47892	,27463	
<i>I feel satisfied with my chances for salary increases.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	3,8689	1,71732	,21988	,744
	Senior Manager	29	3,3793	1,56784	,29114	
<i>There are benefits we do not have which we should have.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,5902	1,54248	,19749	,185
	Senior Manager	29	4,5517	1,24172	,23058	
<i>I like my supervisor.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	3,2787	1,51802	,19436	,900
	Senior Manager	29	3,7241	1,72992	,32124	
<i>I have too much paperwork.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	2,9508	1,84776	,23658	,241
	Senior Manager	29	2,0690	1,46217	,27152	
<i>I don't feel my efforts are rewarded the way they should be.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,8361	1,62461	,20801	,117
	Senior Manager	29	4,8621	1,78734	,33190	
<i>I am satisfied with my chances for promotion.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,7213	1,70422	,21820	,947
	Senior Manager	29	4,6897	1,69249	,31429	
<i>There is too much bickering and fighting at work.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	3,0328	1,83455	,23489	,934
	Senior Manager	29	2,8621	1,84631	,34285	
<i>My job is enjoyable.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,5574	1,51134	,19351	,683
	Senior Manager	29	4,9655	1,45118	,26948	
<i>Work assignments are not fully explained.</i>	Middle level Manager	61	4,3443	1,71158	,21915	,224
	Senior Manager	29	4,5172	1,47892	,27463	

4.12.3. Age (One-Way Anova)

In contrast, age had a big impact on the responses of the participants. As shown in Table 14, statistically significant differences were observed in the following statements: There is really too little chance for promotion on my job; My supervisor is quite competent in doing his/her job; When I do a good job, I receive the recognition for it that I should receive; Those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted; My supervisor is unfair to me; I do not feel that the work I do is

appreciated; My efforts to do a good job are seldom blocked by red tape; I find I have to work harder at my job because of the incompetence of people I work with; People get ahead as fast here as they do in other places; There are benefits we do not have which we should have; I have too much to do at work. The descriptive statistics (analytical results) of these statements classified by age groups are illustrated in table 4.15.

Table 14: One-Way ANOVA Analysis age)

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
<i>I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do.</i>	Between Groups	16,366	3	5,455	2,788	,245
	Within Groups	168,257	86	1,956		
	Total	184,622	89			
<i>There is really too little chance for promotion on my job.</i>	Between Groups	42,805	3	14,268	7,428	,000
	Within Groups	165,195	86	1,921		
	Total	208,000	89			
<i>My supervisor is quite competent in doing his/her job.</i>	Between Groups	45,531	3	15,177	6,207	,001
	Within Groups	210,291	86	2,445		
	Total	255,822	89			
<i>I am not satisfied with the benefits I receive.</i>	Between Groups	17,889	3	5,963	2,104	,106
	Within Groups	243,711	86	2,834		
	Total	261,600	89			
<i>When I do a good job, I receive the recognition for it that I should receive.</i>	Between Groups	27,554	3	9,185	3,102	,031
	Within Groups	254,668	86	2,961		
	Total	282,222	89			
<i>Many of our rules and procedures make doing a good job difficult.</i>	Between Groups	20,709	3	6,903	2,511	,064
	Within Groups	236,447	86	2,749		
	Total	257,156	89			
<i>I like the people I work with.</i>	Between Groups	5,219	3	1,740	,897	,446
	Within Groups	166,781	86	1,939		
	Total	172,000	89			
<i>I sometimes feel my job is meaningless.</i>	Between Groups	5,264	3	1,755	1,320	,273
	Within Groups	114,291	86	1,329		
	Total	119,556	89			
<i>Communications seem good within this organization.</i>	Between Groups	8,213	3	2,738	1,892	,137
	Within Groups	124,409	86	1,447		
	Total	132,622	89			

	Total	132,622	89			
<i>Raises are too few and far between.</i>	Between Groups	19,005	3	6,335	3,061	,133
	Within Groups	173,859	84	2,070		
	Total	192,864	87			
<i>Those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted.</i>	Between Groups	32,937	3	10,979	7,825	,000
	Within Groups	120,663	86	1,403		
	Total	153,600	89			
<i>My supervisor is unfair to me.</i>	Between Groups	44,169	3	14,723	8,499	,000
	Within Groups	148,987	86	1,732		
	Total	193,156	89			
<i>The benefits we receive are as good as most other organizations offer.</i>	Between Groups	3,258	3	1,086	1,542	,209
	Within Groups	60,564	86	,704		
	Total	63,822	89			
<i>I do not feel that the work I do is appreciated.</i>	Between Groups	22,584	3	7,528	7,440	,000
	Within Groups	87,016	86	1,012		
	Total	109,600	89			
<i>My efforts to do a good job are seldom blocked by red tape.</i>	Between Groups	22,418	3	7,473	4,754	,004
	Within Groups	135,182	86	1,572		
	Total	157,600	89			
<i>I find I have to work harder at my job because of the incompetence of people I work with.</i>	Between Groups	32,790	3	10,930	7,992	,000
	Within Groups	117,610	86	1,368		
	Total	150,400	89			
<i>I like doing the things I do at work.</i>	Between Groups	7,081	3	2,360	1,044	,378
	Within Groups	194,519	86	2,262		
	Total	201,600	89			
<i>The goals of this organization are not clear to me.</i>	Between Groups	15,997	3	5,332	2,459	,068
	Within Groups	186,492	86	2,169		
	Total	202,489	89			
<i>I feel unappreciated by the organization when I think about what they pay me.</i>	Between Groups	31,806	3	10,602	4,559	,005
	Within Groups	200,016	86	2,326		
	Total	231,822	89			
<i>People get ahead as fast here as they do in other places.</i>	Between Groups	41,606	3	13,869	5,547	,002
	Within Groups	215,016	86	2,500		
	Total	256,622	89			
<i>My supervisor shows too little interest in the feelings of</i>	Between Groups	8,718	3	2,906	1,635	,187
	Within	152,882	86	1,778		

<i>subordinates.</i>	Groups					
	Total	161,600	89			
<i>The benefit package we have is equitable.</i>	Between Groups	13,925	3	4,642	2,073	,110
	Within Groups	192,564	86	2,239		
	Total	206,489	89			
<i>There are few rewards for those who work here.</i>	Between Groups	17,336	3	5,779	2,096	,107
	Within Groups	237,064	86	2,757		
	Total	254,400	89			
<i>I have too much to do at work.</i>	Between Groups	30,082	3	10,027	3,689	,015
	Within Groups	233,741	86	2,718		
	Total	263,822	89			
<i>I enjoy my coworkers.</i>	Between Groups	13,440	3	4,480	2,134	,102
	Within Groups	180,516	86	2,099		
	Total	193,956	89			
<i>I often feel that I do not know what is going on with the organization.</i>	Between Groups	2,018	3	,673	,374	,772
	Within Groups	154,604	86	1,798		
	Total	156,622	89			
<i>I feel a sense of pride in doing my job.</i>	Between Groups	13,877	3	4,626	2,421	,072
	Within Groups	164,345	86	1,911		
	Total	178,222	89			
<i>I feel satisfied with my chances for salary increases.</i>	Between Groups	6,382	3	2,127	,749	,526
	Within Groups	244,107	86	2,838		
	Total	250,489	89			
<i>There are benefits we do not have which we should have.</i>	Between Groups	27,509	3	9,170	4,977	,003
	Within Groups	158,447	86	1,842		
	Total	185,956	89			
<i>I like my supervisor.</i>	Between Groups	4,584	3	1,528	,594	,621
	Within Groups	221,372	86	2,574		
	Total	225,956	89			
<i>I have too much paperwork.</i>	Between Groups	14,628	3	4,876	1,580	,200
	Within Groups	265,372	86	3,086		
	Total	280,000	89			
<i>I don't feel my efforts are rewarded the way they should be.</i>	Between Groups	6,747	3	2,249	,802	,496
	Within Groups	241,075	86	2,803		
	Total	247,822	89			
<i>I am satisfied with my chances for</i>	Between Groups	10,639	3	3,546	1,251	,297
	Within Groups					

<i>promotion.</i>	Within Groups	243,850	86	2,835		
	Total	254,489	89			
<i>There is too much bickering and fighting at work.</i>	Between Groups	33,303	3	11,101	3,607	,117
	Within Groups	264,652	86	3,077		
	Total	297,956	89			
<i>My job is enjoyable.</i>	Between Groups	,989	3	,330	,143	,934
	Within Groups	198,299	86	2,306		
	Total	199,289	89			
<i>Work assignments are not fully explained.</i>	Between Groups	7,629	3	2,543	,951	,420
	Within Groups	229,971	86	2,674		
	Total	237,600	89			

In particular, as the age increases the level of job satisfaction also increase. This is not stand for participants who were more than 51 years old, since the number of their responses was low (N=4). Generally, the age group of 41-50 exhibited the highest levels of job satisfaction.

Table 15: One-Way ANOVA Analysis (age) - Analytical Results, Descriptive Statistics
Descriptives

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
<i>There is really too little chance for promotion on my job.</i>	18-30	8	3,2500	1,58114	,55902	1,9281	4,5719	1,00	5,00
	31-40	44	3,7091	1,29072	,19458	4,5167	5,3015	2,00	6,00
	41-50	34	4,9059	1,50815	,25865	3,1797	4,2321	1,00	6,00
	51+	4	5,5000	,57735	,28868	4,5813	6,4187	5,00	6,00
	Total	90	4,3333	1,52875	,16114	4,0131	4,6535	1,00	6,00
<i>My supervisor is quite competent in doing his/her job.</i>	18-30	8	3,0500	1,58114	,55902	1,9281	4,5719	1,00	5,00
	31-40	44	3,2545	1,63472	,24644	3,9575	4,9515	1,00	6,00
	41-50	34	4,4588	1,49628	,25661	2,5367	3,5809	1,00	6,00
	51+	4	5,0000	1,15470	,57735	3,1626	6,8374	4,00	6,00
	Total	90	3,8444	1,69541	,17871	3,4893	4,1995	1,00	6,00
<i>When I do a good job, I receive the recognition for it that I should receive.</i>	18-30	8	3,8235	1,60357	,56695	3,1594	5,8406	3,00	7,00
	31-40	44	4,5000	1,69628	,25572	4,2570	5,2884	2,00	7,00
	41-50	34	4,7727	1,81693	,31160	3,1896	4,4575	1,00	7,00
	51+	4	6,0000	1,15470	,57735	4,1626	7,8374	5,00	7,00
	Total	90	4,4444	1,78074	,18771	4,0715	4,8174	1,00	7,00
<i>Those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted.</i>	18-30	8	3,7647	1,06904	,37796	3,1063	4,8937	3,00	5,00
	31-40	44	4,0000	1,16684	,17591	4,4634	5,1729	2,00	6,00
	41-50	34	4,8182	1,28060	,21962	3,3179	4,2115	1,00	5,00
	51+	4	6,0000	,00000	,00000	6,0000	6,0000	6,00	6,00
	Total	90	4,4000	1,31371	,13848	4,1248	4,6752	1,00	6,00
<i>My supervisor is unfair to me.</i>	18-30	8	3,8235	1,90863	,67480	2,6543	5,8457	2,00	6,00
	31-40	44	4,2500	1,08419	,16345	4,8522	5,5114	2,00	6,00
	41-50	34	5,1818	1,48672	,25497	3,3048	4,3423	1,00	6,00
	51+	4	6,0000	,00000	,00000	6,0000	6,0000	6,00	6,00
	Total	90	4,6222	1,47319	,15529	4,3137	4,9308	1,00	6,00
<i>I do not feel that the work I do is</i>	18-30	8	4,4706	,00000	,00000	6,0000	6,0000	6,00	6,00
	31-40	44	5,0000	,93443	,14087	5,0341	5,6023	3,00	6,00

<i>appreciated.</i>	41-50	34	5,8182	1,21194	,20785	4,0477	4,8935	2,00	6,00
	51+	4	5,5000	,57735	,28868	4,5813	6,4187	5,00	6,00
	Total	90	5,0667	1,10971	,11697	4,8342	5,2991	2,00	6,00
<i>My efforts to do a good job are seldom blocked by red tape.</i>	18-30	8	4,0000	,53452	,18898	5,0531	5,9469	5,00	6,00
	31-40	44	4,8636	1,26842	,19122	4,4780	5,2493	1,00	6,00
	41-50	34	5,5000	1,39262	,23883	3,5141	4,4859	2,00	6,00
	51+	4	5,0000	,00000	,00000	5,0000	5,0000	5,00	5,00
	Total	90	4,6000	1,33071	,14027	4,3213	4,8787	1,00	6,00
<i>I find I have to work harder at my job because of the incompetence of people I work with. 4,0588</i>	18-30	8	4,0588	,75593	,26726	4,3680	5,6320	4,00	6,00
	31-40	44	5,0000	1,17856	,17767	4,8690	5,5856	2,00	6,00
	41-50	34	5,2273	1,27781	,21914	3,6130	4,5047	2,00	6,00
	51+	4	6,0000	,00000	,00000	6,0000	6,0000	6,00	6,00
	Total	90	4,8000	1,29996	,13703	4,5277	5,0723	2,00	6,00
<i>People get ahead as fast here as they do in other places.</i>	18-30	8	3,0000	1,30931	,46291	1,9054	4,0946	1,00	4,00
	31-40	44	3,4182	1,59611	,24062	3,8329	4,8034	1,00	6,00
	41-50	34	4,3706	1,67396	,28708	2,8865	4,0547	1,00	6,00
	51+	4	1,5000	,57735	,28868	,5813	2,4187	1,00	2,00
	Total	90	3,7556	1,69806	,17899	3,3999	4,1112	1,00	6,00
<i>There are benefits we do not have which we should have.</i>	18-30	8	3,2500	2,05287	,72580	1,5338	4,9662	1,00	6,00
	31-40	44	4,3636	1,11211	,16766	4,5255	5,2017	2,00	6,00
	41-50	34	4,8529	1,51522	,25986	3,8243	4,8816	1,00	6,00
	51+	4	6,0000	,00000	,00000	6,0000	6,0000	6,00	6,00
	Total	90	4,5778	1,44547	,15237	4,2750	4,8805	1,00	6,00
<i>I have too much to do at work.</i>	18-30	8	3,2500	1,38873	,49099	4,0890	6,4110	3,00	6,00
	31-40	44	4,1364	1,62239	,24458	3,6431	4,6296	1,00	6,00
	41-50	34	5,2059	1,80117	,30890	3,0774	4,3343	1,00	6,00
	51+	4	6,0000	,00000	,00000	6,0000	6,0000	6,00	6,00
	Total	90	4,1556	1,72171	,18148	3,7949	4,5162	1,00	6,00

4.12.4. Educational Level

Finally, the educational level did not influence the levels of job satisfaction of seafarers, since no statistically significant differences were identified (see Table 16).

Table 16: One-Way ANOVA Analysis (educational level)

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
<i>I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do.</i>	Between Groups	8,335	2	4,168	2,057	,134
	Within Groups	176,287	87	2,026		
	Total	184,622	89			
<i>There is really too little chance for promotion on my job.</i>	Between Groups	6,101	2	3,050	1,314	,274
	Within Groups	201,899	87	2,321		
	Total	208,000	89			
<i>My supervisor is quite competent in doing his/her job.</i>	Between Groups	10,865	2	5,433	1,929	,151
	Within Groups	244,957	87	2,816		
	Total	255,822	89			
<i>I am not satisfied with the benefits I receive.</i>	Between Groups	8,569	2	4,285	1,473	,235
	Within Groups	253,031	87	2,908		
	Total	261,600	89			
<i>When I do a good job, I receive the</i>	Between Groups	16,351	2	8,175	2,675	,075
	Within Groups					

<i>recognition for it that I should receive.</i>	Within Groups	265,871	87	3,056		
	Total	282,222	89			
<i>Many of our rules and procedures make doing a good job difficult.</i>	Between Groups	5,298	2	2,649	,915	,404
	Within Groups	251,858	87	2,895		
	Total	257,156	89			
<i>I like the people I work with.</i>	Between Groups	1,141	2	,571	,291	,749
	Within Groups	170,859	87	1,964		
	Total	172,000	89			
<i>I sometimes feel my job is meaningless.</i>	Between Groups	4,407	2	2,203	1,665	,195
	Within Groups	115,149	87	1,324		
	Total	119,556	89			
<i>Communications seem good within this organization.</i>	Between Groups	6,229	2	3,114	2,144	,123
	Within Groups	126,394	87	1,453		
	Total	132,622	89			
<i>Raises are too few and far between.</i>	Between Groups	5,051	2	2,525	1,143	,324
	Within Groups	187,813	85	2,210		
	Total	192,864	87			
<i>Those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted.</i>	Between Groups	5,822	2	2,911	1,714	,186
	Within Groups	147,778	87	1,699		
	Total	153,600	89			
<i>My supervisor is unfair to me.</i>	Between Groups	7,103	2	3,551	1,661	,196
	Within Groups	186,053	87	2,139		
	Total	193,156	89			
<i>The benefits we receive are as good as most other organizations offer.</i>	Between Groups	,010	2	,005	,007	,993
	Within Groups	63,812	87	,733		
	Total	63,822	89			
<i>I do not feel that the work I do is appreciated.</i>	Between Groups	17,370	2	8,685	8,193	,101
	Within Groups	92,230	87	1,060		
	Total	109,600	89			
<i>My efforts to do a good job are seldom blocked by red tape.</i>	Between Groups	6,247	2	3,123	1,795	,172
	Within Groups	151,353	87	1,740		
	Total	157,600	89			
<i>I find I have to work harder at my job because of the incompetence of people I work with.</i>	Between Groups	7,315	2	3,658	2,224	,114
	Within Groups	143,085	87	1,645		
	Total	150,400	89			
<i>I like doing the</i>	Between	3,037	2	1,519	,665	,517

<i>things I do at work.</i>	Groups					
	Within Groups	198,563	87	2,282		
	Total	201,600	89			
<i>The goals of this organization are not clear to me.</i>	Between Groups	6,813	2	3,407	1,515	,226
	Within Groups	195,676	87	2,249		
	Total	202,489	89			
<i>I feel unappreciated by the organization when I think about what they pay me.</i>	Between Groups	1,526	2	,763	,288	,750
	Within Groups	230,296	87	2,647		
	Total	231,822	89			
<i>People get ahead as fast here as they do in other places.</i>	Between Groups	6,251	2	3,125	1,086	,342
	Within Groups	250,371	87	2,878		
	Total	256,622	89			
<i>My supervisor shows too little interest in the feelings of subordinates.</i>	Between Groups	13,472	2	6,736	3,956	,233
	Within Groups	148,128	87	1,703		
	Total	161,600	89			
<i>The benefit package we have is equitable.</i>	Between Groups	6,214	2	3,107	1,350	,265
	Within Groups	200,275	87	2,302		
	Total	206,489	89			
<i>There are few rewards for those who work here.</i>	Between Groups	3,097	2	1,549	,536	,587
	Within Groups	251,303	87	2,889		
	Total	254,400	89			
<i>I have too much to do at work.</i>	Between Groups	6,176	2	3,088	1,043	,357
	Within Groups	257,646	87	2,961		
	Total	263,822	89			
<i>I enjoy my coworkers.</i>	Between Groups	10,420	2	5,210	2,470	,091
	Within Groups	183,536	87	2,110		
	Total	193,956	89			
<i>I often feel that I do not know what is going on with the organization.</i>	Between Groups	,081	2	,041	,023	,978
	Within Groups	156,541	87	1,799		
	Total	156,622	89			
<i>I feel a sense of pride in doing my job.</i>	Between Groups	3,503	2	1,752	,872	,422
	Within Groups	174,719	87	2,008		
	Total	178,222	89			
<i>I feel satisfied with my chances for salary increases.</i>	Between Groups	1,543	2	,771	,270	,764
	Within Groups	248,946	87	2,861		
	Total	250,489	89			

<i>There are benefits we do not have which we should have.</i>	Between Groups	4,857	2	2,428	1,167	,316
	Within Groups	181,099	87	2,082		
	Total	185,956	89			
<i>I like my supervisor.</i>	Between Groups	1,642	2	,821	,318	,728
	Within Groups	224,314	87	2,578		
	Total	225,956	89			
<i>I have too much paperwork.</i>	Between Groups	8,896	2	4,448	1,427	,246
	Within Groups	271,104	87	3,116		
	Total	280,000	89			
<i>I don't feel my efforts are rewarded the way they should be.</i>	Between Groups	2,494	2	1,247	,442	,644
	Within Groups	245,328	87	2,820		
	Total	247,822	89			
<i>I am satisfied with my chances for promotion.</i>	Between Groups	3,776	2	1,888	,655	,522
	Within Groups	250,713	87	2,882		
	Total	254,489	89			
<i>There is too much bickering and fighting at work.</i>	Between Groups	2,982	2	1,491	,440	,646
	Within Groups	294,973	87	3,390		
	Total	297,956	89			
<i>My job is enjoyable.</i>	Between Groups	2,881	2	1,440	,638	,531
	Within Groups	196,408	87	2,258		
	Total	199,289	89			
<i>Work assignments are not fully explained.</i>	Between Groups	3,472	2	1,736	,645	,527
	Within Groups	234,128	87	2,691		
	Total	237,600	89			

5.

DISCUSSION

Taking demographic characteristics of participants first into consideration, it was highly important and desired that research participants were diverse in terms of their demographic characteristics, so that research findings are not biased by certain characteristics of respondents. More specifically, it was important that research participants varied in terms of their gender, so that female seafarers also have the ability to express themselves about a profession that is mainly male-dominated and most of its features refer to noise, vibrations, stress and fatigue, which shall normally influence seafarers of different genders in different ways. It was also important and interesting that research participants also differed in terms of their age, which is associated with their years of experience as seafarers. This means that research findings derived from younger – less experienced and older- more experienced seafarers, thereby being more representative of the wider population of seafarers under discussion. Being all senior officers, it was highly expected that participants would hold a university of Master’s degree, as well as that they would all be medium or higher-level managers. Although this added to the credibility of research findings, it would be even more desired for the sample to comprise of even more high-school graduates, so that the voice of simple seafarers occupied with daily routine tasks and hazards is heard to a bigger extent in the research.

Regarding satisfaction with payment, as research findings indicated, this was found to be at moderate levels with respect to the sample of seafarers that participated in the research, Under no doubt, based on the analysis of Armstrong (2006), wages and salaries form one of the most important issues and challenges that HR managers in organizations of all sectors, industries and types have to deal with. At the same time, the analysis of Spector (1997) shall also be taken into account, according to which salaries and their potential increases are fundamental objective factors that always determine job satisfaction. The average level of satisfaction of the sample’s seafarers with their salary, as well as the potential to earn an increase in their earnings, could be put forward to explain why it is difficult to retain existing highly-skilled seafarers, as

well as attract young people to enter the shipping industry. Following the analysis of Branch (2007), especially for the case of such a challenging and hazardous profession as that of seafarers, financial incentives are highly important, even if there are some people for whom such incentives do not correspond to the primary needs that they wish to satisfy through their job. At least, it is positive that seafarers of the sample stated that they are satisfied with the benefits they are offered in their organization, at least from the moment that they are fairly allocated among them, as well as they are at least those expected, taking into account the special nature of the profession of seafarers. Indeed, based on the analysis of Armstrong (2006), benefit schemes are vital tools in the context of effectively managing human resource, while at the same time also being one of the factors that determine employee satisfaction. Also, taking into account the analysis and findings of Nguyen et al. (2014), benefit plans are crucially important for the highly stressful occupation of seafarers. Therefore, research findings indicate that shipping companies in Greece have moved to the correct direction in terms of offering the expected benefits to their seafarers, even if they do not pay them so well, after all, always at least with respect to the opinions and perceptions of the 90 Greek seafarers that participated in this research.

As far as promotion is concerned, research findings indicated that Greek seafarers enjoy a fair chance of being promoted to a higher job position, if they are good at what they do. Again based on the analysis of Branch (2007), this is also another incentive that would help in retaining seafarers. Of course, based on the research findings of Dalkrani & Dimitriadis (2018), promotion is not one of the factors that has been found to influence employee commitment to their organization. However, it remains one of the factors that lead to employee satisfaction with their job. As such, taking the high importance of job satisfaction both in general (e.g. Bakotic, 2013) and in the particular case of the shipping industry (e.g. McVeigh et al, 2019; Yuen et al., 2018), it is highly important that seafarers in Greece are happy with their promotion opportunities, which is in turn important for retaining seafarers, even if this could mean that promotional incentives would not prevent them from switching to another organization in the industry. Taking participants' responses in the above, it was also expected that they would also declare their satisfaction with the rewarding their performance in their organization as well. Indeed, based on the research findings of Dalkrani & Dimitriadis (2018), rewards for recognizing one's efforts is also a very

important determinant of job satisfaction, although again this does not ensure that seafarers shall keep on working in the same organization, which may be important for every single shipping company, but not so important for the wider shipping industry as a whole, when the aim of a research is to understand why there is lack of skilled labour in the industry.

The satisfaction of the seafarers of the sample with their promotional and reward incentives was not verified also in the case of their supervisors. Indeed, research findings indicated that seafarers are on average not so highly satisfied with the skills of their supervisors, as well as the extent to which their supervisors effectively deal with the issues, challenges and worries that seafarers are subject to. Based on the analysis of Spector (1997), the relationship between employees and their supervisors is a major determinant of job satisfaction. This implies that Greek shipping companies, as well as shipping companies in other parts of the world, shall place high emphasis on this major aspect of HRM, which as it seems also highly applies in the case of crew management in the shipping industry as well. At least, research findings indicated that the seafarers of the sample were found to be highly satisfied with the communication aspects in their organization, which Harwood (2018) suggests that it is also another very important factor determining that seafarers' job satisfaction. Of course, Harwood (2018) mostly referred to the case of very diverse workforces, which have to find ways of effective communication, in order for seafarers to manage their level of stress with their job. In any case, though, shipping companies need to build effective ways of communication even when their workforces are more homogeneous in terms of their demographic characteristics. If the findings for communication are combined with the findings for supervisors, then it follows that Greek seafarers must mostly communicate well with each other and not with their supervisors, which, as analyzed above, it is a matter of serious concern for the management of shipping companies.

Operating conditions was also one of the factors in which the seafarers of the research sample were not found to be so highly satisfied with. There is no doubt that this does not mean that seafarers expressed a dissatisfaction with the operating conditions they have to face. In any case, though, their percentage of satisfied seafarers was not so high as expected, with low percentages in terms of paperwork being at the forefront. This was somehow expected, if it is taken into account that the sample consisted of

seafarers in managerial positions, who are often assigned with a lot of paperwork, due to the nature of their work. The above findings could imply that Greek shipping companies could make some efforts towards reducing paperwork, taking into consideration, of course, that this is hard to avoid in the case of key managerial positions.

Research findings were highly optimistic in terms of the level of satisfaction of participants with their coworkers. Indeed, it is highly optimistic that the majority of participants were found to like working with the other people that also work in their organization, as well as that conflicts are rare and seafarers do not have to work harder, in order to cover the inconsistency and lack of capabilities of their peers. Based on the analysis provided by Spector (1997), satisfaction with peers is an important determinant of job satisfaction in general, which in turn, as it has been thoroughly analyzed so far in this research project, highly determines employee retention. Therefore, findings in this research may also indicate that seafarers in Greek shipping companies like the people they work with, which is also highly important, if the findings and analysis of Harwood (2018) are taken into account, whereby having to cope with different people is one of the major stressors that seafarers have to deal with in their workplace, also being a factor that is likely to prevent them from continuing working in their shipping company, as well as the shipping industry in general.

It was analyzed in the second chapter of this project that job tasks and the nature of work themselves are also important determinants of employee motivation and job satisfaction (Spector, 1997; Bakotic, 2013). For the particular case of the occupation of seafarers, it was also analyzed in the second chapter that the hazardous working conditions and tasks that seafarers have to deal with on a daily basis are important stressors in their workplace, which, among others, are likely to cause their physical and mental fatigue, which shall prevent their retention in the industry (Besikci et al., 2015; Allianz Global, 2019). Hopefully, the above were not verified in the case of the shipping officers of the sample. This may indicate that Greek shipping companies allocate human resources and tasks efficiently. It may also indicate that seafarers are well-trained and adequately skilled to perform their daily tasks. It may indicate both of the above assumptions, both of which are important HR aspects and at the same time important determinants of job satisfaction. No matter what interpretation is

given, it seems certain that seafarers in Greece, at least with respect to the sample of 90 seafarers that participated in this research, are satisfied with their tasks and it seems that they perform the tasks they expected to perform. In turn, this indicates that recruitment and selection, whose importance has also been promoted by Collings & Wood (2009), have been on average successful in the Greek shipping industry, since seafarers are called to perform the duties they expect and shipping companies have selected those seafarers that have the potential to perform such duties with excitement and commitment.

A notable and at the same time expected up to a point finding of the primary research that was held for the purposes of this project was that female participants were found to be less satisfied than men with respect to certain dimensions of job satisfaction that were tested in the research, with fairness of payment, chance of promotion, skills of supervisors, job recognition, benefits offered by their company, clearness of corporate goals and effective communication, as well as meaning of occupation being at the forefront. Under no doubt, based on the hazards and the physical tasks that seafarers have to deal with on a daily basis, as these are through described by researchers like Oldenburg et al. (2010), Hystad & Eid (2016) and Gander et al. (2008) among others, it would be reasonable to assume that female seafarers should normally find the occupation of seafarers more difficult than their male counterparts. Especially if the hazards of social isolation and distance from family are taken into account, together with the difficulty in maintaining a balance between family and working life, as the above are described by researchers like Oldenburg et al. (2009), Carotenuto et al. (2013) and Jepsen et al. (2015), it would be normal to consider that it would be mostly female participants that would possibly express a dissatisfaction with the difficulties they have to face in their shipping experience. However, research findings do not indicate that it is such hazards and on-the-job difficulties that make female seafarers feel dissatisfied. Rather, it becomes evident from research findings that female seafarers feel that they are recognized in the same way and are not subject to the same opportunities as their male peers. Given that in modern times female executives are more highly present in professions traditionally perceived as male-specific, it follows that the shipping industry is still a male-dominated domain, at least of the responses of the research sample are taken into consideration. It could derive from the above that shipping companies in Greece and other countries need to offer more equal

benefits and opportunities to seafarers, so that the industry becomes more attractive for female seafarers as well, who could also solve part of the problem of lack of skilled labour in the shipping industry. The above could further add to the attractiveness of the occupation of seafarers, both for male and female potential shipping executives, especially as far as operating conditions and life-balance challenges are concerned.

As far as the relationship between job position and job satisfaction is concerned, the parametric tests that were held showed a slight correlation between the two variables and only in terms of job recognition, rules and regulations that have to be followed and the extent to which seafarers like working with their peers. In the above three aspects, research findings showed that senior managers expressed higher levels of satisfaction, compared with their middle-level counterparts. On the one hand, as mentioned before, it could be considered as normal that senior managers are more positive in terms of dealing with rules and regulations, since this is something that they already expect, when they get promoted at a higher-level managerial position in a global industry that is highly regulated. On the other hand, though, the particular research findings also indicate that Greek shipping companies need to place higher emphasis on the job-recognition aspects of their HR policies and practices. Indeed, in consistency with the theoretical framework developed by Armstrong (2006) and O'Sullivan (2014), job recognition is a very important aspect of HRM in organizations and it is also one of the factors that for some employees is a great motivator. Such a motivator could further make the seafarers' occupation attractive, thereby further contributing to attracting skilled labour in an industry that highly needs them.

Research findings regarding age were also very interesting. Indeed, it was indicated by research findings that the older seafarers are, the higher is their job satisfaction. On the one hand, this was somehow surprising, given that as years pass by, seafarers should become more tired of the hazards and difficulties they experience on board, thereby also become less and less satisfied. If the variables and aspects of job satisfaction that were analyzed in this research are taken into account, though, in consistency with findings regarding job position, it becomes evident that seafarers in higher positions in the hierarchy of their organization and with more years of experience are more satisfied with their job. Based on the findings so far, one reason is certainly the higher job recognition that managers at higher levels enjoy. Further to

that, though, it must also be the fact that older shipping executives are more experienced in dealing with the emergencies and hazards of the seafarers' business, thereby also gradually becoming more satisfied with their job, especially if they build an ability to perform their tasks easier and quicker. The above do not also have to do with the educational background of seafarers, though. Indeed, as the research findings indicate, the educational level of seafarers was not found to influence their levels of job satisfaction. This was an expected research findings, since existing academic literature and previous research findings, as presented and analyzed in the second chapter of this research project, do not also verify such an empirical relationship.

6.

CONCLUSION

6.1. Summary of Findings and Implications

The main aim of current dissertation was to investigate the levels of job satisfaction of Greek maritime officers. In relevance with this aim, the project had the following objectives:

- To determine the overall level of job satisfaction among Greek maritime officers
- To examine the extent to which subcomponents of job satisfaction influence overall satisfaction among Greek maritime officers.
- To examine if the levels of job satisfaction of Greek maritime officers are differentiated according to their demographic characteristics (gender, age, position in the company, educational level).

Overall, the results indicated that shipping managers who are working in the Greek shipping industry illustrated high levels of Job satisfaction, revealing the dynamics and the potential of the domestic maritime sector. By using the JSS scale developed by Spector (1994) it was found that the overall score of job satisfaction of Greek seafarers was 158; according to Spector (1994), a total score higher than 144 reveals job satisfaction. Therefore, the Greek shipping industry managed to develop a working climate that satisfies the people that are working in it. The four factors in which participants revealed the highest levels of job satisfaction were (in order of importance): communication, nature of work, fringe benefits and contingent rewards. In contrast, weaknesses in terms of job satisfaction were identified in: supervision, pay, and operating conditions. Moreover, the levels of job satisfaction were differentiated according to gender, age and position in the company. On the other hand, educational background did not influence the responses of seafarers. In particular, men, seniors and older employees illustrated significant higher levels of job satisfaction compared to women, middle level manages and younger officers respectively. However, shipping firms should apply practices for improving the levels

of job satisfaction of females and middle level managers (who in most of the cases are younger) for ensuring equity and fairness inside the organization.

Research findings have very important implications, both theoretical and practical ones. On the theoretical side, research findings indicate that crew management is a highly complex concept and process, which is even more complex than traditional HRM, when other sectors are discussed. Under no doubt, most HRM concepts are common for all sectors and industries. However, when examining the specific case of the shipping industry and the occupation of seafarers, special conditions and hazards associated with the particular profession shall always be taken into account. Further to the above, job satisfaction was also found to be a very complex and multidimensional concept. Most importantly, apart from some factors, which are considered as factors that objectively influence job satisfaction, researchers shall always have in mind that different employees are motivated by different needs and factors, the satisfaction of which shall also determine employees' overall job satisfaction.

As far as practical implications are concerned, these mainly have to do with the findings regarding seafarers working in Greek shipping companies. Indeed, research findings indicate that Greek shipping companies have done a lot to maintain the satisfaction of their seafarers. Up to a point, this shall explain why the Greek shipping industry is at the top of the global shipping industry, comprised of skilled seafarers that are satisfied with what they are offered in their job and that also acknowledge why it is worth being occupied with this profession. However, research findings also indicated that Greek shipping firms should improve supervision conditions, salaries and operating aspects for improving further the levels of job satisfaction of their employees. Considering the strong linkages between performance and job satisfaction, improvements in the aforementioned factors have vital importance for maintain the success and leadership of the Greek shipping industry in a global context. Through the above, it is more likely that the shipping company will continue to occupy its skilled seafarers, while at the same time attracting more skilled men and women to join the industry, characterized by objective hazards and difficulties that only skilled and satisfied seafarers can manage. In conclusion, job satisfaction is a critical issue that had been accurately addressed by Greek maritime organizations. Nevertheless, there is room for improvement in the certain field. If the domestic shipping sector wants to play a leading role in global landscape should give particular

emphasis in job satisfaction determinants. In this context, the weaknesses mentioned in the current research should be taken under consideration.

6.2. Research Limitations and Suggestions for Further Research

Last but not least, this dissertation was subject to some methodological limitations. To start with, the research that was held was a quantitative one. Although this gave the ability of extracting measurable and more objective research findings and conclusions, quantitative research does not allow participants to freely express their views and respond in their own way, which would give deeper insights regarding seafarers' satisfaction and its relation with their retention in the industry, as well as the attraction of new ones. Therefore, future studies could use also qualitative research methods for examining the discussed problem in greater depth. Next to that, although the research sample of 90 participants was found to be adequate enough for producing objective and reliable results, future researchers could having more time and resources could conduct the same research with larger samples, which would be even more representative of the wider population of seafarers under investigation. In the same context, the research was held with Greek seafarers only. Other papers can distribute questionnaires in shipping executives that are working in firms located in different countries for making comparisons. Last but not least, this study examined job satisfaction only in the context of seafarers' retention and in the context of dealing with the problem of lack of an adequate number of skilled seafarers occupied in the shipping industry. Future studies can examine the impact of job satisfaction on other aspects as well, such as, for example, on performance and employee engagement in the domestic shipping industry.

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APPENDIX

Research Questionnaire

JOB SATISFACTION SURVEY Paul E. Spector Department of Psychology University of South Florida Copyright Paul E. Spector 1994, All rights reserved.							
PLEASE CIRCLE THE ONE NUMBER FOR EACH QUESTION THAT COMES CLOSEST TO REFLECTING YOUR OPINION ABOUT IT.		Disagree very much Disagree moderately Disagree slightly Agree slightly Agree moderately Agree very much					
1	I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do.	1	2	3	4	5	6
2	There is really too little chance for promotion on my job.	1	2	3	4	5	6
3	My supervisor is quite competent in doing his/her job.	1	2	3	4	5	6
4	I am not satisfied with the benefits I receive.	1	2	3	4	5	6
5	When I do a good job, I receive the recognition for it that I should receive.	1	2	3	4	5	6
6	Many of our rules and procedures make doing a good job difficult.	1	2	3	4	5	6
7	I like the people I work with.	1	2	3	4	5	6
8	I sometimes feel my job is meaningless.	1	2	3	4	5	6
9	Communications seem good within this organization.	1	2	3	4	5	6
10	Raises are too few and far between.	1	2	3	4	5	6
11	Those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted.	1	2	3	4	5	6
12	My supervisor is unfair to me.	1	2	3	4	5	6
13	The benefits we receive are as good as most other organizations offer.	1	2	3	4	5	6
14	I do not feel that the work I do is appreciated.	1	2	3	4	5	6
15	My efforts to do a good job are seldom blocked by red tape.	1	2	3	4	5	6
16	I find I have to work harder at my job because of the incompetence of people I work with.	1	2	3	4	5	6
17	I like doing the things I do at work.	1	2	3	4	5	6
18	The goals of this organization are not clear to me.	1	2	3	4	5	6

	PLEASE CIRCLE THE ONE NUMBER FOR EACH QUESTION THAT COMES CLOSEST TO REFLECTING YOUR OPINION ABOUT IT. Copyright Paul E. Spector 1994, All rights reserved.	Disagree very much Disagree moderately Disagree slightly Agree slightly Agree moderately Agree very much
19	I feel unappreciated by the organization when I think about what they pay me.	1 2 3 4 5 6
20	People get ahead as fast here as they do in other places.	1 2 3 4 5 6
21	My supervisor shows too little interest in the feelings of subordinates.	1 2 3 4 5 6
22	The benefit package we have is equitable.	1 2 3 4 5 6
23	There are few rewards for those who work here.	1 2 3 4 5 6
24	I have too much to do at work.	1 2 3 4 5 6
25	I enjoy my coworkers.	1 2 3 4 5 6
26	I often feel that I do not know what is going on with the organization.	1 2 3 4 5 6
27	I feel a sense of pride in doing my job.	1 2 3 4 5 6
28	I feel satisfied with my chances for salary increases.	1 2 3 4 5 6
29	There are benefits we do not have which we should have.	1 2 3 4 5 6
30	I like my supervisor.	1 2 3 4 5 6
31	I have too much paperwork.	1 2 3 4 5 6
32	I don't feel my efforts are rewarded the way they should be.	1 2 3 4 5 6
33	I am satisfied with my chances for promotion.	1 2 3 4 5 6
34	There is too much bickering and fighting at work.	1 2 3 4 5 6
35	My job is enjoyable.	1 2 3 4 5 6
36	Work assignments are not fully explained.	1 2 3 4 5 6